

D8.7: Living Network Strategy Report

Handover - November 2022

Status of deliverable: Public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 776816

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1. Introduction

As part of Project Ô's long-term legacy, we aim to foster the development of a community of practice relating to collaborative development of a circular water economy and environmental sustainability. This document presents the strategy for creating this community of practice or 'living network'.

The strategy leverages the strengths of the project's participatory approach to water sustainability innovation, including collaborative and co-production models of fostering pro-environmental change. The network should foster expanded community capabilities in topics such as stakeholder engagement, impact evaluation, evidence-based sustainability communication and social innovation. The core beneficiaries for this network are those working in water reuse across a wide range of disciplines, with a particular focus on researchers and related professionals (see Figure 1 for indicative coverage for the living network).

The strategy outlined in this document foresees several practical actions to bring the network to life and sustain its development:

1. establishment of a membership scheme for the living network,
2. creation of a community website with hosted resources to incentivise its ongoing use and sharing to expand the network,
3. an initial programme of events aimed at drawing in potential members,
4. training provision for members (and non-members) in the network.

This interlinked series of actions can establish a foundation for informal gatherings and communications to develop through bottom-up processes based on network member interests. This will help to ensure the relevance and utility of the network for addressing real-world member needs.

In this way, the strategy foresees a combination of top-down and bottom-up initiatives ultimately constituting the living network as a long-term, sustainable community of practice.

Figure 1: Water sustainability scope - indicates coverage for living network

2. Strategic planning

Strategies are necessary to build a sense of direction for a network, and to lay the foundations for its long-term sustainability. This community of practice should have an overarching focus on evidence-based practice, with a specialism in **water sustainability**.

Over time, it should interlink with the constellation of EU projects focused on water sustainability and establish links between water-focused projects and the wider universe of relevant expertise in evidence-based practice. There can be links that show the bigger picture of sustainability trends (e.g., EU funding, UN Sustainable Development Goals, UNESCO policy initiatives) but there also needs to be limitations, such as not extending too far into a focus on consumer goods or supply chain management.

While this document and the initial efforts within the project lifespan should establish a direction and tentative boundaries for the living network, it is fully anticipated that these components can evolve organically based on the membership body of the living network.

For this reason, the strategy cannot be excessively prescriptive. Substantial space for decisions must be maintained so that the membership can be the primary driver of the network. This should ensure the network's relevance to the membership and improve the sense of ownership that can be important for making the network self-sustaining in the long-term.

3. General principles and clarifications

There is an overarching need for any network to be relevant, beneficial or of community interest, and solve common problems experienced by the member base. Often, a sense of community develops out of efforts to turn ideas into actionable, pragmatic goals, address challenges or change existing forms/structures of collaboration. Such clarifications can help a community ground itself in the motivations, goals or benefits that they wish to achieve.

As such, a network should enable members to work together, synergise and formulate mutually beneficial collaborations based on complementary skills

or resources. The network can be represented at conferences, contribute to papers, workshops, events or other activities to engage and ground itself in the community.

The following represent crucial points that have been considered in the development of this strategy:

- **Clarification of shared challenges:** In a practical sense, being specific about the methods and tools through which goals can be achieved.
 - This may also include actionable recommendations or suggested interventions specific to the context.
 - This includes knowledge about mutual needs. The growth and importance of ‘working groups’ small enough can allow for more collaboration.
- **Clarification of shared goals:** Networks can be implemented as projects that are aimed at specific goals. Communication around the shared goal to “make a change” and “impact society in a positive way”.
- **Clarification of shared activities:** Several strategies to build network synergies and complementarity, most notably through specific network activities. The crucial and most common process was that of ensuring members worked together on projects on a regular basis.
- **Clarification of shared resources:** Creation of resources relevant to the research context of the network which is made to be accessible to the researchers. information diffusion and knowledge exchange mechanisms for improving the diffusion of new ideas and practices.
- **Clarification of shared interests:** Specific common interests can be grouped by a level of expert knowledge on issues.
- **Clarification of recognition mechanisms:** Another important strategy to build community was creating **recognition mechanisms** for projects or individual organisations who have achieved something within their organisations or project work.

- These recognition mechanisms help members feel valued for their contributions to the network, thereby further developing their sense of being ‘part’ of it.
- Participants often note that recognition mechanisms should be carefully thought through and tailored to what members would value most.
- **Skill-based categorisation** where it is recognized that certain members have specialized skills or practical expertise and they could be grouped so their skills could be applied towards certain projects which required them.

4. Network orientation

This network should foster a vibrant community of professionals working to develop a more sustainable future. This includes people working in water sustainability projects, as well as many other domains of social, cultural and environmental sustainability. Our community aims to solve problems, find solutions, and make a difference in how the world works.

People will be encouraged to join the network to achieve the following:

Increase your impact

Learn new methods and approaches

Explore solutions and find best practices

Advance your career

Connect with your peers to advance the field

5. Key Challenge: Financial Viability

Most newly established networks can expect a range of issues that challenge sustained engagement and long-term financial solvency. In early stages, challenges may include complexities of coordination, accountability concerns, instability, coordination difficulties and costs, leadership and management gaps, loss of autonomy, conflict and power issues.

From an operational standpoint, challenges include limited finances, time, staffing (whether voluntary or compensated) or other resource issues relating to (potential) members may affect the network's growth or negatively impact its efficiency. Proactively addressing such challenges from the outset is essential to ensuring the long-term viability of the network, and therefore its potential to deliver impact.

From a financial management perspective, the planned starting point is for the non-profit educational and research charity, Institute for Methods Innovation, to provide the structure and support to launch the network in collaboration with other project partners. This is intended to ensure that there is a legal entity that can underpin the initial work of setting up and maintaining the network, drawing on existing expertise and resources in related network-building activities.

Having a legal entity in place as the technical home for the network before the formal end of the project is also a necessity to ensure that efforts to establish the community of practice continue into the post-project period. Ultimately, however, the network's membership may choose to establish the living network as an independent legal entity or choose any other structure that fits the long-term goals of the network.

As such, it is important to recognise that efforts to ensure networks are financially sustainable can be of utmost importance. Most new networks need a lean core team to minimise costs that can be functionally agile and responsive. Membership fees, services such as training, and other avenues for monetisation are often the primary sources for a network's follow-up funding after EU funding finishes. Network expansion can also occur as projects fund new working groups. Here, we plan to connect our Living Network to other EU-

funded projects wherever feasible, as well as ensuring a steady flow of revenue through provision of useful training and other services. The advertising strategy will start with other EU-funded projects on similar topics, seeking to gain their buy-in and assistance in promoting the network. This will support a bottom-up network growth that can sustain long-term financial viability.

6. Living Network - Membership

Here we have prepared example website text to demonstrate the membership dimension of the community of practice. Prior to the end of the project, a website presence for the network should be established, initially housed under the existing project website. Over time, it is expected that the network should establish its own website.

Living Network

Through this network, we promote the application of high-quality social research and evaluation methods, practical advice and evidence-based best practices.

By becoming a member, you will be joining a community working to develop projects and events, rooted in evidence-based practice.

We work to connect researchers and practitioners to promote [research impact praxis](#).

We are a global network with diverse members around the world.

**Join today for access to the latest research, meet peers
and develop your own research knowledge!**

Membership benefits

Depending on the tier of membership best suited to your needs, we offer the following benefits:

Newsletter sharing the latest research and member events

Inclusion on our member's directory and the ability to advertise consultancy services

Discounted access to events, training opportunities and workshops¹

Use of our software to develop and monitor your own tailored surveys

Invitations to exclusive member events

Support publishing your findings

Access to a global professional network and research opportunities

Support with professional development, including our unique professional accreditation

And that's not all!

Choose a membership tier to find more about each specific offer.

Individual Membership Categories

We offer different levels of membership. They're tailored to reflect your career journey and organisational needs. Click on a level to find out more.

Three tiers of individual memberships		
Level 1 Entry	Level 2 Basic	Level 3 Professional

¹ Strategic approach to be considered: Advertise all events with some labelled as members-only and targeted to specific member levels as an incentive to subscribe to higher levels of membership

<i>Free</i>	<i>Paid</i>	<i>Paid</i>
Organisational member²		

Entry³ (Level 1)

If you're new to evidence-based practice or maybe you just want to find out more about us, then the free subscription could be a good choice for you.

Sign up to receive:

Our newsletter/chat/listserv/discussion board to foster connection between members

Invitations to public and member-only* events, workshops, conferences, training and networking opportunities

Access to our public member directory

Free ready-to-use templates

Low discount on training courses

**Membership required to attend member-only events*

Basic (Level 2)

Maybe you're a student, a volunteer or just new to visitor research, if so this level is for you. It's also designed to appeal to those who've retired but still want to keep up to date, share their expertise and connect with the sector. It can be a great way to find out more about the benefits of a higher level membership or retain membership during quieter periods of your career.

² Organisational members may host and propose events, as well as sponsoring activities in the network.

³ Free subscriber level newsletters should include advertisements/promotions for paid membership level services, to encourage them to join

As well as all the benefits given to free subscribers (Level 1), you'll receive:

Access to resources aimed at supporting early-career researchers and practitioners in evidence-based public engagement and evaluation

Opportunities to connect with later career professionals through events and workshops

Discounted entry to public events, and access to member-only events, workshops, conferences, training and networking opportunities

Events introducing you to peers and similar organisations, encouraging collaboration and support

An overview of the latest research findings tailored to your sector and interests

The option to have your profile listed on our public member directory to help connect with and find your peers

Access to customised template surveys, including your very own dashboard to monitor your findings

Professional (Level 3)

As the highest level of individual membership, we recommend this for mid- to senior career professionals and those with the regular involvement implementing or applying visitor research.

As well as all the benefits given to subscribers and all other levels of membership, you'll receive:

Invitations to exclusive workshops and events

The option to advertise consultancy services on our public members directory*

Opportunity to advertise your visitor-research related events on our website event calendar and in our regular newsletter

Ability to create fully tailored self-build surveys for your research

Option to attend an annual tailored workshop exploring your institution's finding and developing practical applications

Support creating case studies of good practice for public dissemination (one per year)

Option to collaborate on producing research publications or a conference event proposal drawing on your results**

**for those holding accreditation*

***where appropriate methods are used*

The greatest opportunity for full members is the chance to participate in our accreditation course. This unique course will support your professional development and provide you with individual certification reflecting your skill and ability in visitor research.

Have you chosen the level of membership suitable for you?

Join us in a few clicks today

	Monthly*	Annual
Level 1 - Entry	Free	Free
Level 2 - Basic	€XX	€XXX
Level 3 - Professional	€XX	€XXX
Organisational	€XX	€XXX

**Minimum 12 month membership applies*

Enter your details here to subscribe to our free services:

Contact Information

First name

Last name

Primary Email Address

Tell us more about yourself

In which country do you currently reside?

(Start typing to find in the list.)

How would you describe your current working status?

What is your highest educational qualification?

What are you hoping to gain from this network?

How did you hear about this network?

When ready, please click Submit below to finalize your subscription.

SUBMIT

7. Events and live workshops

To be attractive and valuable, the network needs resources that are perceived as relevant and useful to people right away, including access to training courses, products (e.g., templates, online library), and live events that focus on the practical level.

Events should further develop/engage members in subjects/topics, with the following as a starting list for further discussion.

1. **Training for early career professionals in water sustainability:** Support development of skills to help them stand out from the crowd with job applications.
2. **Highlighting the importance of interdisciplinary approaches, including social sciences and humanities, in water reuse:** There are a range of skills from the social sciences and humanities that would benefit the delivery of effective water reuse projects.
3. **How to use your research findings to make a difference:** helping optimise the use of research findings and help them translate them into recommended actions.
4. **Professional capacity building:** can be used on a few different levels:
 - a. Encouraging organisation to gain interdisciplinary skills and highlighting the benefits of doing so,
 - b. Encouraging those already doing interdisciplinary water reuse work to expand capacity further,
 - c. Tailoring this capacity building to enable different levels of stakeholder involvement and engagement in water reuse projects.
5. **Survey design** - training in how to use surveys and showing the advantages of creating tailored surveys for a range of purposes. Includes developing the skills needed to fully utilise survey tools and digital methods of data collection and analysis.

6. **How to write successful funding proposals** that include stakeholder engagement, responsible research, public engagement and other elements - from two perspectives.
7. **How to publish your findings/how to write a report** - A series of workshops walking participants through the steps needed to publish their findings:
 - a. How to write a research report for different types of audiences - what is needed, formatting, referencing, etc.
 - b. Where to publish or present your report/article - including how to tailor your dissemination for various audiences, e.g. journal article, popular press, conference presentations, peer presentations.
8. **How to manage your data in a way that is GDPR compliant** - This workshop provides practical guidance on how to set up data management systems and practices in a way that can ensure both legal compliance and efficiency in subsequent stages such as data analysis and ultimately open data publishing.
9. **Professional development certification** - Establishing expertise in the topics covered in a verifiable way with the living network providing official certification.

Such network activities can be attractive and valuable when perceived as relevant and useful.

Network Training Workshops: A concrete example

Live workshops can be valuable ways to build relationships within the network, and also to extend the reach of the network to those seeking new skills. Below, an example live workshop is described.

How to make a difference in water sustainability policy with your research

Live workshop aimed at water sustainability researchers

Making an effective plan for creating policy impact with your research can increase your likelihood of success. This training will introduce you to the differences in culture between research and policy and provide you with tools to chart your path to impact. Speakers will introduce the cultural differences between research and policy, impact objectives, impact logic models and theories of change, with practical examples drawn from water sustainability research and policy. The workshop will provide concrete examples, drawing on real-world research and policy experience from the speakers.

In this hands-on workshop, you will have the opportunity to start developing your water policy impact plans with expert advice and support.

There are a wide range of potentially valuable workshops that could be developed by those within the network as well as invited external experts. It is anticipated that the leadership of the network should suggest topics and workshops, as well as soliciting recommendations (and feedback) from the membership.

Crucially, all events and training workshops should be empirically assessed to ensure that there an equitable and inclusive experience is being provided. Finally, quality of experience and impacts on personal and professional levels should also be evaluated at least periodically.

8. Conclusion

Establishing a successful living network means delivering value to researchers and other stakeholders involved in water reuse, building on the particular expertise in participatory approaches to sustainability innovation implementation demonstrated in this project.

Here, we have set out a strategy for standing up and launching a network that delivers such value for its members. The project partners are committed to pursuing this vision in the time remaining in the project and especially in the months and years that follow.

There is a clear opportunity to build on the interdisciplinary expertise represented in this project, as well as other EU-funded projects focusing on water sustainability. This expertise can form the basis of a community of practice that builds capacity to deliver research and innovation that really makes a difference.